

USING OF MODERN EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT: The article reveals new methods of effectiveness increase in teaching foreign languages to students using information and communication technologies and their practical implementation at universities. Adoption of information and communication technologies to the educational process is based on students' independent language learning that encourages more productive development of language competences mastered by students and future specialists in a special area of technical knowledge as a whole.

Key words: modern educational technologies, international communication, motivating learners, integration, communicative competence, computer technology.

The rapid and radical changes taking place in modern society, advances in the theory and practice of learning English make the education system need to update the content and methods of using innovative technologies in foreign language teaching. Education must meet modern needs and realities, use not only the experience and experience of past years but also implement modern technologies, develop relevant teaching methods and techniques. "In a globalized world, methods of learning and teaching foreign languages must be better adapted to the ever-changing needs and conditions of language learners. New technologies open up huge opportunities for enhanced individualization of learning". Like all areas, education must develop and keep pace with transformations and metamorphoses in society. Teaching approaches and methods are being modernized with the emergence of new opportunities. Today the educational process in the country's educational institutions is being reformed by global requirements for the quality of education: informatization of the educational space, integration processes in modern domestic education, establishing cooperation with foreign educational institutions in the field of education and research, international exchanges and more. According to E.N. Voronova, "the system of the teacher's work to ensure the learning outcomes of a foreign language must necessarily include the implementation of the following technologies: the technology of communicative learning, the technology of

understanding the communicative meaning of the text, gaming technology, learning technologies in cooperation, project technologies, etc.” [1, 189].

One of the modern tools for teaching English to students can be the use of podcasting in the learning process. Podcasts began to be used in 2004 for the transmission of audio or video broadcasts on the Internet. The word “podcast” comes from English iPod and broadcast and means an audio or video file that “is distributed free of charge via the Internet for mass listening or viewing” [2, 109]. Educational podcasts devoted to the study of foreign languages, allow solving a number of methodological tasks, including the formation of auditory skills and understanding of speaking foreign languages, the formation and improvement of listening skills, the expansion and enrichment of lexical vocabulary, the formation and improvement of grammatical skills, development skills of speaking and writing. Effective innovative educational technologies are also TED video conferences and video blogs. The topics of intelligent TED conferences and speeches are extensive, including a wide variety of topics: from science, culture, art, politics and global problems, business to technology, design and entertainment. TED comes from the English language and translates as technologies, entertainment, design (Technology Entertainment Design).

Today, TED is a world community, inviting to cooperate in the search for a deeper understanding of the world and the desire to change it for the better people of all kinds (from professionals to enthusiasts) representing different cultures. The main objective of this non-profit organization is to spread unique ideas that its founders believe should be informed by “ideas worth spreading”, and inspire and inspire people around the world to learn something new, share knowledge and experience, thereby making the world a better place. So, these ideas are presented to listeners in the format of a short speech (no more than 18 minutes). On the official website of TED.com, reference information on research and development is freely available and everyone can learn the information they are interested in, communicate in real time, and participate in TED conferences and events that take place all year round in different countries. TED is an innovation-cultural and information project. On the one hand, for someone TED is an inexhaustible source of inspiration and a search for unique ideas, for others it is a good opportunity to share their ideas, developments, and projects. TED is a kind of source that can be useful for a wide range of users: both for professionals and professionals, and for students of various specialties studying foreign languages. TED is a quality modern educational resource, which can be used in practical classes in English. In addition, it is suitable for independent

work and learning foreign languages. Video creates images and causes certain associations that contribute to better perception, assimilation and memorization of information.

In addition, when watching video lectures, the subtitle function is available, which helps users to understand the information more fully. The lecture topics are diverse and relevant. This resource is useful for students not only in teaching foreign languages, but also in mastering the skills of speaking to the audience. Using video materials TED Talks is perfect for analyzing public speeches, reflecting on proposed topics, improving the skills of oratory. Lectures allow students to demonstrate the various options for speaking before the public, to consider many ways of presenting information, the ability to build communication with listeners, to establish contact, enter into a dialogue and get feedback. In addition, there is an opportunity to get acquainted with the speeches of speakers, which inspires students to develop a unique strategy of speaking to the audience and an individual way of communicating with their listeners. In addition, on the site as an example, photos and video presentations and materials are demonstrated and constantly uploaded.

Students use this resource both in everyday life and in preparation for classes. Students have the opportunity to choose lectures and speeches on lessons learned, get additional information and learn about the latest discoveries and trends on the topic of interest to them. Consequently, students not only practice foreign languages, but also expand their professional knowledge and skills in this or that sphere.

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